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Editorial

Being Humanely Human

The French philosopher Paul Ricoeur has claimed that “Every understanding is self-understanding.” When we try to understand other human beings or any technique, we are throwing more light ourselves.

It is in this context that we need to perceive the meaning of the Delphic maxim, “know thyself” (“Γνώθι Σεαυτόν”, or “Gnothi Seauton”)

Knowing ourselves truly leads us to understand appreciate how human beings are. It leads us to ask questions like: Who am I? How do I know? Who is a human being? What are our concerns? How do we undemand ourselves in the context of the larger world? Who is a human being? What is our responsibility to others? How can truly appreciate our humane nature?

To be humane is our sacred task. This encourages us to be compassionate not only to fellow-human beings and ever the larger world. It challenges us to treat others with kindness and compassion. Compassion urges us people to go out of our way to help the physical, mental, or emotional pains of others,

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including animals and plants. This compassion also must embrace the technological and scientific dimensions of ourselves.

Confronted with our technological success or progress, we are called to be responsible to ourselves and the larger reality. We are called to be both human and humane to ourselves and the other (including animals and techniques like Artificial Intelligence and Robots).

The world we live in is in urgent need of compassion, joy and hope. Can we be messengers of such joy and hope by making this world more compassionate, humane and inclusive.

So this issue of *Vidyankur* urges the readers to cultivate our sense of compassion, so that we become truly human (to ourselves) and humane (to all others). May we experience the joy of living, the abundance of loving and the fullness of sharing with others!

The Editor